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ANARCHO-SYNDICALISM: FIGHTING AND STRATEGY
IN THE XXI CENTURY

*Sashcheko R.S., Postgraduate Student,
Scientific Supervisor – PhD, Associate Professor Barsuk I.A.
Belarusian State University*

The modern capitalist world-system, developing under the auspices of neoliberal economic policy, generates many contradictions in the context of the modern development of the planetary society. In particular: it does not offer a solution to the problem of poverty, contributes to the increase in income inequality and well-being of the population, does not provide a living wage for billions of workers, does not provide the necessary number of jobs in the era of increasing automation of production, does not fully provide social protection for the population, exploits the environment and natural resources, focuses only on GDP growth, allows the privileged class to ignore the economic interests of the majority of the world's population. In view of the above, modern economic programs and practices need to be restructured and innovative elements introduced, which in turn leads many researchers to turn to alternative (unorthodox) economic approaches. The theorists of libertarian socialism in the form of anarcho-syndicalism made a significant contribution to the development and popularization of alternative concepts.

Anarcho-syndicalism is a political philosophy and anarchist school of thought that views revolutionary industrial unionism or syndicalism as a method for workers in capitalist society to gain control of an economy and thus control influence in broader society. The end goal of syndicalism is to abolish the wage system, regarding it as wage slavery. The anarcho-syndicalist theory therefore generally focuses on the labor movement.

The basic principles of anarcho-syndicalism are solidarity, direct action (action undertaken without the intervention of third parties such as politicians, bureaucrats and arbitrators) and direct democracy, or workers' self-management. Anarcho-syndicalists believe their economic theories constitute a strategy for facilitating proletarian self-activity and creating an alternative cooperative economic system with democratic values and production that is centered on meeting human needs. Anarcho-syndicalists perceive the primary purpose of the state as the defense of private property in the forms of capital goods and therefore of economic, social and political privilege. In maintaining this status quo, the state denies most of its citizens the ability to enjoy material independence and the social autonomy that springs from it.

The most prominent American-German anarchist historian, Rudolf Rocker, presented a systematic concept of the development of libertarian socialism in the direction of anarcho-syndicalism. In his work «Anarcho-syndicalism: theory and practice», R. Rocker notes that “the problem that is

being posed to our time is to free man from the curse of economic exploitation, political and social enslavement, i.e., in "reconstructing the economic life of peoples from scratch and building it in the spirit of socialism". Thus, the program of anarcho-syndicalism proposes the construction of an economic system of libertarian socialism, i.e. "without the state and capitalist masters", the real political content of which will be a "radically democratic society" that preserves the maximum possible amount of individual freedoms. For an anarchist, freedom is not an abstract philosophical concept, but a vital concrete opportunity for each person to bring to full development all the forces, abilities and talents that nature has endowed him with, and turn them to social development. To solve this problem, the key elements, according to the thinker, are the producers themselves (workers' syndicates), since they are the only element of society that creates value, from which a new future can arise. Their task is to free labor from economic exploitation, free society from all institutions and procedures of political power, and open the way to a union of free associations based on cooperative labor and planned economic management in the interests of the whole society. To prepare the working people for this great goal and to rally them together as a militant force is the main task of anarcho-syndicalism.

Anarcho-syndicalists seek to organize with order militant workers who agree with their revolutionary aims and principles. Initially, this takes the form of local groups and industrial networks, but as these grow in size and influence they can begin to take on union functions such as advising fellow workers and initiating direct action like work-to-rules, strikes and occupations. The role of anarcho-syndicalist networks and unions is not to try and recruit every worker, but to advocate and organize mass meetings of all workers involved in each struggle so that the workers involved retain control. Within these mass meetings, anarcho-syndicalist argue for the principles of solidarity, direct action and self-organization. Instead, anarcho-syndicalism unites the political and the economic and opposes representation in the flavor of self-organization. By organizing this way, workers learn to act for themselves, exercising their power without being led by union officials or political vanguards, calling into question the way society is organized and prefiguring the world we want to create, without bosses or rules: libertarian socialism.

By direct action, the Anarcho-Syndicalists mean every method of immediate warfare by the workers against their economic and political oppressors. Among these, the outstanding are the following: strike, in all its gradations from the simple wage-struggle to the general strike; the boycott; sabotage in its countless forms; anti-militarist propaganda; and in particular critical cases, such, for example, and resistance of the people for the protection of life and liberty.

Among these fighting techniques the strike, that is, organized refusal to work, is the most used.

In its simplest form, it is for the workers an indispensable means of raising their standard of living or defending their attained advantages against the concerted measures of the employers. But the strike is for the workers not only a means for the defense of immediate economic interests, but it is also continuous schooling for their powers of resistance, showing them every day that every least right has to be won by an unceasing struggle against the existing system.

Direct action by organized labor finds its strongest expression in the general strike, in the stoppage of work in every branch of production by the organized resistance of the proletariat, with all the consequences arising from it. It is the most powerful weapon which the workers have at their command and gives the most comprehensive expression to their strength as a social factor.

All these methods of the daily struggle of the workers' unions should give them a social character and ultimately lead to the triumph of socialism. To achieve the complete and final emancipation of the workers is possible only under one condition: the appropriation of capital, i.e., raw materials, all tools of labor, including land, by all workers, through a social revolution that will dismantle the state apparatus and expropriate capital from the capitalists.